

FEATURES OF ANXIETY- DEPRESSION DISORDERS IN MEN AND WOMEN WITH HIV

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of a study comparing the severity of anxiety and depression in HIV-positive patients depending on gender. Clinical manifestations of anxiety and depression differed between men and women, emphasizing the need for a gender-oriented approach in diagnosis and treatment.*

Keywords: *anxiety, HIV-positive patients, depression, men, women.*

Introduction. Anxiety-depressive disorders are among the most common mental health conditions that significantly impact quality of life, work capacity, and social functioning. In patients with chronic illnesses, such as HIV infection, these disorders are even more prevalent due to the combined effects of biological factors and psychosocial stressors, including stigma, isolation, and fear of the future [5, 6].

The gender aspect of anxiety-depressive disorders holds particular importance in mental health research. Women and men exhibit notable differences in both the severity and nature of anxiety and depression symptoms. Women are more likely to present with emotional symptoms, such as hypervigilance, emotional lability, and somatization tendencies. Men, on the other hand, often experience functional impairments, irritability, and decreased social activity. These differences are influenced by a combination of biological, psychological, and social factors, including hormonal fluctuations, cultural expectations, and coping mechanisms [1, 2, 3].

The study of anxiety-depressive disorders becomes especially relevant in the context of HIV infection [4]. Women living with HIV often face additional stressors, such as caregiving responsibilities and societal discrimination, while men are less likely to seek psychological support, resulting in more severe outcomes of depression. Failure to diagnose and treat anxiety-depressive disorders in a timely manner exacerbates the progression of the primary disease, reduces adherence to antiretroviral therapy, and increases the risk of HIV progression [7, 8].

Despite the critical importance of this issue, there is a lack of comprehensive data on gender differences in anxiety and depression among HIV-positive patients. This gap hinders the development of effective psychological support programs that account for gender-specific features. Analyzing these differences is crucial for creating personalized treatment and prevention strategies aimed at improving the mental health and overall well-being of patients.

In conclusion, studying the features of anxiety-depressive disorders in men and women with HIV infection is a pressing issue. Addressing this gap will not only enhance the psychological state of these patients but also improve the overall efficacy of medical care and disease management [11].

Gender differences in the manifestations of anxiety and depressive states remain an important research area. Women are more prone to emotional instability, hypersensitivity, and somatization, while men predominantly experience functional impairments and reduced social

activity [9,10]. Understanding these differences allows for more individualized approaches to diagnosis and treatment, highlighting the relevance of this topic.

Early detection and correction of anxiety-depressive disorders in HIV-positive patients are essential for improving their psychological well-being, adherence to therapy, and preventing further complications. Despite the importance of this issue, gender differences in the clinical presentation of mental health disturbances in this patient group remain insufficiently studied, underscoring the need for further research [12].

The aim of the study is to investigate and compare the severity of anxiety and depression in HIV-positive patients depending on gender.

Material and methods. HIV-positive patients from AIDS prevention and control centers who were under outpatient observation after being diagnosed with HIV were examined. Experimental-psychological, laboratory and mathematical-statistical methods of research were used. To assess anxiety and depression, a range of psychometric clinical scales with varying validity levels were used. Symptom severity was measured using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), and Zung Depression Scale.

Results and discussion. The study revealed significant prevalence of depressive and anxiety syndromes among HIV-positive patients. Clinical manifestations of anxiety and depression differed between men and women, allowing the identification of some characteristic symptoms for each group. The conducted studies have shown the presence of depressive and anxiety syndrome in a significant number of HIV-infected patients examined. Based on the study, the clinical manifestations of anxiety and depression differed between men and women, which allows us to identify some characteristic features of the symptoms in each group. Men were characterized by the predominance of mild and moderate forms of anxiety. There are often complaints of irritability, tension, and difficulty concentrating. Somatic symptoms such as tachycardia and excessive sweating are less common. Anxiety is often associated with social isolation and fear of disclosure of the diagnosis. Depressive symptoms included decreased mood, apathy, feelings of worthlessness and guilt. Physical symptoms included general weakness, sleep disorders (insomnia or hypersomnia), and decreased appetite. Men were more likely to report a decrease in their ability to work and a loss of interest in professional activities. Somatic symptoms of anxiety were expressed in women: a feeling of "lump in the throat", dizziness, muscle tension, rapid heartbeat, subclinical and pronounced forms of anxiety prevailed.

There are often fears related to the future (children's health, possible stigmatization), as well as increased suspiciousness. In women, anxiety is often accompanied by tearfulness and emotional lability.

Women have more pronounced psychoemotional symptoms of depression: feelings of hopelessness, suicidal thoughts, tearfulness. There is a tendency to introspection, self-deprecation and an emphasis on the negative aspects of life. Physical symptoms included loss of strength, headaches, menstrual irregularities, lack of appetite, or, conversely, episodes of overeating. Women are more likely to complain of loneliness and lack of support.

The results obtained on different scales, depending on the gender of the subjects, are presented below.

According to HADS data, subclinical forms of anxiety and depression are more common in women, especially those aged 20-29 years. Mild to moderate forms of anxiety and depression prevail in men (Table 1).

Table 1

Anxiety and Depression Features by Gender (HADS)

Gender	Subclinical Anxiety (%)	Severe Anxiety (%)	Subclinical Depression (%)	Severe Depression (%)
Men	12.5 ± 1.48	8.2 ± 1.12	14.3 ± 1.72	10.5 ± 1.34
Women	31.5 ± 2.65	18.9 ± 1.98	25.8 ± 2.34	16.7 ± 2.12

The Beck scale shows similar results: women are more likely to suffer from depressive states, including severe forms (Table 2).

Table 2

Levels of depression depending on gender on the Beck Depression Scale

Gender	Mild Depression (%)	Moderate Depression (%)	Severe Depression (%)
Men	15.4 ± 1.89	10.8 ± 1.32	7.5 ± 1.21
Women	28.6 ± 2.76	18.4 ± 2.12	12.9 ± 1.97

The Zung scale confirms the data, indicating a more pronounced degree of depression in women (Table 3).

Table 3

Levels of depression depending on gender on the Zung scale

Gender	Mild Depression (%)	Moderate Depression (%)	Severe Depression (%)
Men	16.2 ± 1.95	9.8 ± 1.27	6.3 ± 1.14
Women	30.4 ± 2.89	21.5 ± 2.34	15.8 ± 2.01

Based on the analysis, women show more pronounced emotional manifestations of anxiety and depression, including somatization and suspiciousness. Men are more likely to focus on the functional aspects of depression and anxiety, such as decreased performance and irritability. In women, clinical symptoms are often more acute and diverse, which requires a more individualized approach to treatment.

The correlation between the levels of anxiety and depression in men and women was assessed based on data obtained using the hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), the Beck depression scale and the Tsung depression scale. Correlation analysis was performed separately for men and women. In women, there is a stronger correlation between anxiety and depression ($r=0.82$, $p<0.01$) compared with men, which may be due to a greater severity of emotional response to stress and somatization ($r=0.68$, $p<0.01$). In men, the relationship between anxiety and depression is somewhat weaker, which is probably due to a lower tendency to emotional openness and an emphasis on functional symptoms. Correlation between mild and moderate depression $r=0.55$; $p<0.05$. The greatest correlation in women was found on the Tsung scale, which confirms their tendency to display somatic symptoms of depression ($r=0.78$; $p<0.01$). Correlation between physical and emotional symptoms of depression in men $r=0.62$; $p<0.01$.

Conclusion. Thus, the study confirmed that anxiety and depression are widespread among HIV-positive patients. More than 30% of women and about 15% of men exhibit subclinical or severe forms of anxiety and depression. Women are more likely to experience severe forms of anxiety and depression, accompanied by somatization (headaches, palpitations) and emotional lability. In men, anxiety-depressive states manifest themselves more functionally, which is expressed in decreased performance, irritability and apathy. The correlation analysis showed that

the levels of anxiety and depression are closely related in both men and women ($p < 0.001$). This indicates the need for comprehensive work with both components, since their mutual reinforcement can worsen the condition of patients. These differences highlight the need for a gender-based approach in diagnosis and therapy. The results obtained emphasize the need to introduce psychological support programs for HIV-positive patients aimed at early diagnosis and correction of anxiety and depression. Special attention should be paid to women who show more pronounced symptoms and are in the early stages of making a diagnosis.

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